

Energy Optimal Trajectory Planning for Electrically Driven Railway Vehicles with Particle Swarm Optimization

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Abstract—This paper deals with the optimization of velocity trajectories for electrically driven railway vehicles w.r.t. the total energy consumption between two successive stops. First, a quasi-static model of the complete power train of a standard railway vehicle is described. Based on four principle operating regimes – acceleration, cruising, coasting, and braking – energy-optimal trajectories are computed by determining the optimal regime sequence. For the optimization of the switching points between these operating states, particle swarm optimization (PSO) is used. The benefits of this approach are pointed out by simulation results using validated train models.

I. INTRODUCTION

One advantage in trajectory planning for railway applications is the previous knowledge about the duty cycles and their properties. In contrast to road-based applications, where a lot of uncertainties (e.g. unscheduled stops or traffic) may affect the driving style, the basic information for a railway travel – like distances, arrival and departure times, speed limits, traffic stops, and altitude profile – is known in advance. This fact can be exploited to determine an energy-optimal velocity trajectory for the overall trip. The optimized trajectory profiles are of high value in intelligent real-train operations either in the form of a driver advice system (DAS) or for an automatic train operation (ATO). The implementation of such an intelligent driving strategy leads to a reduction of both energy consumption and CO_2 emissions, which is beneficial for economic as well as for environmental reasons.

The main objective of this paper is the calculation of the energy-optimal trajectory for an electrically driven railway vehicle. A lot of optimized control strategies for railway vehicles have already been published in the past. Here, dynamic programming is one of the preferred techniques (e.g. [2], [3], [4]). To avoid the high computational effort related to dynamic programming, model-based approaches like [5] and [6] were investigated as well.

In analogy to [5] and [6], this paper utilizes a detailed simulation model in combination with a heuristic switching of the driving states. In this paper, however, the switching points are determined by a particle swarm optimizer.

For this purpose, a detailed simulation model is derived in Sect. II to determine the energy consumption for a specific track and train characteristics. An operating approach for choosing the optimal sequence of driving states is developed

in Sect. III. Here, the objective of Sect. III-A is to describe the main functionality of the trajectory planning module. The optimization problem related to the energy-optimal trajectory planning is stated in Sect. III-B. To minimize the given optimization problem, a particle swarm optimization algorithm is chosen. This optimization technique is briefly discussed in Sect. III-C. The corresponding simulation results are summarized and assessed in Sect. IV, whereas Sect. V concludes the paper and gives an outlook on future work.

II. SIMULATION MODEL

This section presents the implemented simulation model, which corresponds to the so-called OPEUS-tool. It is employed for the calculation of the total energy consumption of the train and offers the possibility to simulate detailed traction topologies of electrically driven railway vehicles. The OPEUS-tool was developed in the framework of the EU-founded project OPEUS, see [1]. Within the OPEUS project, the OPEUS-tool was validated with both experimental data as well as with a verification to other existing train simulation tools.

The presented approach towards an energy-optimal trajectory planning is applicable to several kinds of traction topologies, including electrically driven railways, hybrid drive systems, and classical diesel traction. Nevertheless, the current work focuses on electrically driven railway vehicles, for which a detailed traction chain topology is available.

(a) Traction topology for AC power supply.

(b) Traction topology for DC power supply.

Fig. 1. Traction topology in backward simulation mode.

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The considered traction topologies, which are depicted in

Fig. 1, are generic for a modern electrically driven railway vehicles. They are typically supplied by either an AC power supply (Fig. 1, (a)) or by a DC power supply (Fig. 1, (b)). Within this work, the presented topologies only differ regarding the power supply side of the intermediate circuit.

A. Simulation Model of the Traction Chain

To obtain a realistic calculation of the energy consumption of the overall traction chain, it is advantageous to employ a backward simulation, see [7], which follows the idea of an inverse system model. The backward simulation is based on a block structure that reflects the reverse direction of the physical power flow from the output to the input. Accordingly, the desired output for the backward simulation is given by a fixed velocity profile. Then, the corresponding inputs signals follow from evaluating the inverse dynamics represented by the backward simulation topology. From a control point of view, this is equivalent to a flatness-based approach and the solution of an inverse problem. The desired velocity profile meets all the constraints given by a timetable and is calculated in a separate trajectory planning module, which is the objective of Sect. III-A.

The equation of motion for the railway vehicle is given by

$$k_{rot}M\dot{v} = F_{wheel} - F_{res} - F_{inc}. \quad (1)$$

Here, M denotes the total mass of the vehicle, k_{rot} a factor to account for the additional rotary masses, F_{wheel} the force at the wheel, whereas \dot{v} stands for the vehicle acceleration. A common approach to determine the driving resistances F_{res} is the Davis equation

$$F_{res} = c_0 + c_1v + c_2v^2, \quad (2)$$

which involves three coefficients (c_0, c_1, c_2) for describing the overall resistance in dependence on the vehicle speed $v(t)$. The inclination γ characterizes the inclination force

$$F_{inc} = M\sin(\gamma)g. \quad (3)$$

The requirement to track a desired velocity profile, in compliance with the mechanical properties of the vehicle, leads to a total power request at the wheel P_{wheel} . The energy losses of the included electric traction components – motor, motor converter, absorption circuit, line converter, transformer, auxiliary converter, and an ESS converter – are determined by the evaluation of efficiency maps. The efficiency map for the j -th component is implemented either as a function of the current load power, i.e., $\eta_i = f(P_{load,j})$ (e.g. for the transformer), or in dependence on both load power and angular velocity, i.e., $\eta_j = f(P_{load,j}, \omega_i)$ (e.g. for the electric motor), see Fig. 2.

B. Simulation Model for the Auxiliaries

In addition to the energy losses caused by the traction components, the simulation structure also takes into account the power request P_{aux} of several auxiliaries. As shown in Fig. 3, the electric auxiliaries involve two main terms: The

(a) Efficiency maps as a function of both load and angular velocity. (b) Efficiency curve in dependence on the load.

Fig. 2. Implementation of the efficiency maps.

first one covers auxiliaries that are considered as constant over the duration of the drive cycle, e.g. light systems as well as HVAC systems.

Fig. 3. Electric auxiliaries consisting of auxiliaries with constant power demand and the requested time-varying cooling power.

This constant auxiliary power $P_{aux,const}$ may be adapted regarding the implemented train service or season. The second term stands for the cooling amount $P_{cool,j}$ of every single traction component. This cooling power $P_{cool,j}$ of the j -th traction component is implemented as a function of the component load $P_{cool,j} = f(P_{load,j})$. As a result, the total cooling power request of the traction chain becomes

$$P_{cool} = \sum_{j=1}^{n_c} P_{cool,j}, \quad (4)$$

where n_c represents the number of components within the traction chain. As depicted in Fig. 3, the total auxiliary power results in

$$P_{aux}(t) = P_{aux,const} + P_{cool}(t). \quad (5)$$

Hence, the total power request P_{total} of the vehicle consists of the required traction power P_{trac} as well as of the auxiliary power P_{aux} according to

$$P_{total}(t) = P_{trac}(t) + P_{aux}(t). \quad (6)$$

For the calculation of the total energy consumption

$$E_{total} = \int_{t_0}^{t_f} P_{total}(t)dt, \quad (7)$$

the total power request $P_{total}(t)$ has to be evaluated between the departure time t_0 and the arrival time t_f defined by the duty cycle.

III. ENERGY OPTIMAL DRIVING STYLE

The main objective of this section is the presentation of the optimization approach towards an energy-optimal driving strategy. To determine this strategy, the proposed approach uses four driving states, namely:

- Acceleration - limited by the maximum traction effort and the passenger comfort,
- Cruising - moving at a constant velocity level (no acceleration),
- Coasting - motion without active traction or braking at the wheels,
- Braking - limited by the maximum braking effort as well as the passenger comfort.

Fig. 4 presents an exemplary trajectory profile consisting of an energy-optimal combination of these different driving states.

Fig. 4. Total trajectory profile based on four characteristic driving states.

As shown in Fig. 4, the switching points between these driving states define the individual velocity profile. The switching conditions are implemented within the trajectory planning module and are discussed in the sequel.

A. Operating Strategy of the Trajectory Planning Module

To determine the optimal location of the switching points for a change of the driving states, two trajectory parameters b_c and p_v are introduced. The parameter b_c defines the distance s_c , where coasting will be employed. Given the fixed overall distance s_{end} , the coasting point is calculated as follows

$$s_c = b_c s_{end} \text{ with } b_c \in [b_{c,min} > 0; b_{c,max} < 1]. \quad (8)$$

Beside coasting, the maximum velocity represents a suitable property for the modification of the velocity profile. The desired maximum velocity v_d of the travel segment is given by

$$v_d = p_v \max \{v_{lim,k}\} \text{ with } p_v \in [p_{v,min} > 0; 1]. \quad (9)$$

Here, $v_{lim,k}$ denotes segment-specific speed limits, whereas p_v serves as the second optimization parameter of the desired trajectory. The main impact of the two trajectory parameters p_v and b_c is illustrated in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Trajectory parameters for the specification of the driving strategy.

The braking distance s_b denotes the largest distance possible to initialize braking in compliance with given distance constraints for the next stop or the next speed limit. This point is determined by an evaluation of the equations of motion (see Eq. (1)) in backward-time direction using the maximum braking effort available.

With this parametrisation of the trajectory, the switching points are determined by a trajectory planning module as depicted in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Structure and functionality of the trajectory planning module

The trajectory always starts with the acceleration mode, followed by a sequence of other driving states that are activated as soon as one of the switching conditions I, ..., VI is fulfilled and enforces a new driving state. These switching conditions are chosen as follows:

- I: $(v = v_d) \vee (v = v_{lim})$
- II: $(v < v_d) \wedge (v < v_{lim})$
- III: $(v = v_b) \vee (v > 0)$
- IV: $(s \geq s_c)$
- V: $(s < s_c)$
- VI: $(s \geq s_b) \wedge (v > v_b)$

This functionality of the trajectory planning module allows for several possible trajectory modes – with different character and style. As a simple example with only one speed limit, these trajectory modes are illustrated in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Trajectory modes based on different driving styles.

Here, the red line stands for the all-out mode, which is identical with the time-optimal solution. The all-out mode corresponds to the parameter choice $p_v = 1$ and $b_c = 1$; it is included only for the purpose of expressing the functionality of the trajectory planner module. As it does not comply with the timetable constraints, it does not have practical relevance

and, hence, will not be part of the following discussion.

The green curve characterises a possibility to fulfill the timetable by maximising the amount of coasting. Therefore, the maximum velocity is fixed by the parameter $p_v = 1$, whereas the remaining parameter b_c is determined by a bisection approach in order to meet the time and distance constraints of the timetable.

Another important trajectory mode is represented by the yellow curve, which corresponds to a trajectory without coasting. Here, the timetable constraints are met by the application of a reduced maximum speed. In analogy to the “maximise coasting” approach, the parameter $b_c = b_{c,max}$ is fixed to its maximum value, whereas the other parameter p_v is determined by a bisection algorithm – to calculate the maximum velocity admissible.

In Fig. 7, the bold orange curve indicates all parameter combinations that allow for meeting the timetable. To determine the energy-optimal solution within the set of possible solutions, an optimization using an evolutionary algorithm is performed.

B. Optimization Problem for the Trajectory Planning

In order to fulfill the timetable, the optimization problem towards an energy-optimal solution for a station-to-station drive takes the given time and position constraints into account. The desired departure and arrival information – times t_0, t_f and positions s_0, s_f – are addressed by the following penalty function

$$J_\kappa = \begin{cases} (\kappa_{dr} - (\kappa_f - \kappa_0))^2 & \text{for } |\kappa_{dr} - (\kappa_f - \kappa_0)| > \Delta\kappa \\ 0 & \text{for else,} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

with $\kappa \in \{t, s\}$. Here, Δt and Δs are admissible time and distance differences for the arrival. The evaluation of the simulation model introduced in Sect. II predicts – according to Eq. (7) – the total energy consumption E_{total} of the railway vehicle. The overall cost function is chosen as

$$J = E_{total} + \alpha_t J_t + \alpha_s J_s, \quad (11)$$

where the coefficients α_s and α_t denote positive weights regarding the position and time constraints.

C. Particle Swarm Optimization

As an analytical calculation of the gradient w.r.t. the cost function defined in Eq. (11) is not forthcoming, a gradient-free optimization approach is employed. The chosen particle optimizer, which belongs to the class of evolutionary algorithms and operates without analytical gradient information, is presented in the sequel.

Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) is inspired by the swarm behavior observed in nature. The algorithm was proposed by Kennedy and Eberhard in 1995 ([8]) and was further developed and applied in several cases, see the overviews in [9] and [10]. PSO is has already become a common technique in railway applications, see e.g. [11], where it is used for timetable scheduling as described in [12] and [13].

Within the presented particle swarm optimization, the possible solution candidates are denoted as particles, where $x_{i,k}$ denotes the position of the i -th particle during the k -th iteration.

To cover the individual as well as the social behavior of the swarm, the progress of the set of particles is influenced by the individually best position $p_{i,k}^{best}$ of every single particle as well as the globally best position g_k^{best} of the total swarm. The individually best position is determined by

$$p_{i,k}^{best} = \begin{cases} p_{i,k-1}^{best} & \text{for } J(x_{i,k}) \geq J(p_{i,k-1}^{best}) \\ x_{i,k} & \text{for } J(x_{i,k}) < J(p_{i,k-1}^{best}), \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

whereas the globally best particle position g_k^{best} of the total swarm is given by

$$g_k^{best} = \operatorname{argmin} \left\{ J(p_{i,k}^{best}) \right\}. \quad (13)$$

The position update of the single particles is defined by

$$x_{i,k} = x_{i,k-1} + v_{i,k}, \quad (14)$$

where $v_{i,k}$ stands for the current velocity of the single particle. The velocity of the particle is denoted with

$$v_{i,k} = w_k v_{i,k-1} + r_{1,k} (p_{i,k}^{best} - x_{i,k-1}) + r_{2,k} (g_k^{best} - x_{i,k-1}). \quad (15)$$

Here, w_k describes a decreasing weighting function to consider the movement of the particle itself. The common implementation of w_k is a linear decreasing function

$$w_k = 2 - \frac{2k}{k_{max}}, \quad (16)$$

with k_{max} is the maximum number of iterations. The coefficients $r_{1,k}$, $r_{2,k}$ are randomly determined weighting factors (default PSO setting: $r_{1,k}$, $r_{2,k} \in [0, 2]$ are uniformly distributed variables). Conclusively, the total update of the particle position according to Eq. (12) – Eq. (15) is depicted in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8. Position updates within PSO.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS AND ASSESSMENT

In this section, a specific scenario of practical relevance is simulated, and the driving styles are compared to each other regarding the resulting energy consumption. The specific scenario is a generic high speed train passing three stations (start – intermediate stop – final stop). The occurring speed limits are highlighted in light gray in Fig. 9, where the maximum speed is set to 300 km/h. Further

details regarding the train characteristic (e.g. train mass, traction power, payload, etc.) are defined in detail in [14]. The reference trajectory represents a velocity profile that is characterized by applying the maximum amount of coasting, see the green curve in Fig. 7. As already mentioned in Sect. III-A, this trajectory mode is characterized by utilizing the maximum speed limit ($p_v = 1$), whereas the coasting point is determined by a bisection algorithm. A comparison of this reference profile and the optimized speed profile is shown in Figure 9.

Fig. 9. Velocity profile of the baseline scenario and the energy-optimal solution.

The evaluation of the optimized trajectory profile indicates that the amount of coasting is shortened, whereas the top speed is increased as compared to the baseline profile. This result reflects two contradictory effects defining the energy consumption: On the one hand, a trajectory with a large amount of coasting – where no traction power is required – contributes to a decrease in the energy consumption. Unfortunately, this requires in turn an increased speed level in order to comply with the timetable. On the second hand – as the driving resistance increases quadratically with the velocity –, the avoidance of high speed segments is beneficial for a low energy consumption, see Eq. (2).

Fig. 10 illustrates the particle evolution during the speed profile optimization w.r.t. the first two stops. Each of the nine windows within Fig. 10 depicts the particle distribution for one iteration (blue star), the personal best particle position (red circle) as well as the global best position up to the current iteration (green rectangle). It becomes obvious in Fig. 10 that after a few iterations (at the latest in iteration 5) the personal best particle positions are arranged in a characteristic manner that is equal to the bold orange curve in Fig. 7. This characteristic particle cloud

characterizes the parameter configurations, which allows for fulfilling both the position and time constraints of the timetable ($J_t = J_s = 0$, see Eq. (10)). This behavior will be utilized in future investigations to implement a two step optimization approach, see Sect. IV.

Fig. 10. Evaluation of particle positions for considered example.

The resulting energy consumption for the single station-to-station motion as well as for the total trip are stated in Tab. I. The detailed simulation model allows for both the calculation of energy consumption at the wheel and the calculation of the total net energy.

	Energy in kWh			
	Energy at the catenary		Energy at the wheel	
	Maximum coasting (baseline)	Optimized trajectory	Maximum coasting (baseline)	Optimized trajectory
Station A–B	1013	972	500	481
Station B–C	4042	3712	2850	2417
Total net energy	5055	4684	3350	2898
Total energy savings in kWh	–	371	–	452
Total energy savings in %	–	≈ 7.5	–	≈ 13.5

TABLE I

ENERGY SAVINGS DUE TO THE ENERGY-OPTIMAL DRIVING STYLE

Here, it could be concluded that the amount of energy savings at the wheel level is much bigger than the total

energy savings at the catenary. This effect underlines the advantage of evaluating the detailed traction chain model within the optimization procedure. A pure evaluation of the energy at the wheel level could have led to different results, because the power loss characteristics of the components as well as the auxiliary power are not considered.

The power profiles in Fig. 11 indicate clearly in which phase of the trip energy savings are attained. Especially during long cruising phases with constant velocity, the reduced velocity allows for a significant reduction of the required power.

Fig. 11. Velocity profile of the baseline scenario and the energy-optimal solution.

Furthermore, the optimized trajectory leads to a reduction of the maximum power peaks during the first section, which is advantageous for the power supply via the energy net. During the second section, the additional braking phases are quite negative for the compatibility with the energy net. To take the compatibility with the energy net into account, an additional term in the cost function may be introduced to lower the given power peaks. Such a modified cost function will be part of future research.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK ON FUTURE RESEARCH

In this paper, a model-based optimization of the velocity profile for electrically driven railway vehicles is presented. For the implementation of the velocity profile, a rule-based trajectory planning module is proposed to determine the switching points between the different driving states. For the calculation of an energy-optimal parametrization of for the switching conditions, a Particle Swarm Optimizer (PSO) is employed. This PSO exploits a detailed simulation model of the traction chain topology to quantify the energy usage of the vehicle. For a comparative analysis of the results, the optimization algorithm is applied to a practice-relevant scenario. The corresponding simulation results are closely related to this specific test case. It is to be expected that they will differ for different drive cycles or traction chain characteristics.

On the one hand, future research will focus on a reduction of the computational effort to enable a usage in real train implementations of driving assistance systems (DAS) or automatized train operations (ATO). For this purpose, a modification of the PSO is possible (e.g. alternative subside

functions w_k) as well as an implementation of alternative optimization techniques (e.g. generic strategies like CMA-ES or simulated annealing).

Additionally, it will be investigated whether a two-step optimization approach is advantageous. In a first optimization step, the parameter configurations that allow for fulfilling the timetable are determined (corresponding to the bold orange line in Fig. 7). For this purpose, a multiple extrema seeking optimization approach ([15], [16]) could be in favor. In a second optimization step, the energy-optimal solution is selected among the solution candidates in this reduced set. Moreover, it is planned to apply the optimization to further operating scenarios. Especially, the consideration of altitude profiles will be a topic of future investigations.

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